

Librarian Strategies In Increasing Reading Interest In Majene Society

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Abstract:

Public interest in reading in Indonesia, especially in Majene Regency, is still relatively low. Based on existing data, Indonesia ranks low in global literacy skills, which is a big challenge for librarians in increasing reading interest. This study aims to analyse the strategies implemented by librarians in Majene Regency to increase public interest in reading. The type of research used is descriptive with a qualitative approach. Primary data sources consist of library leaders, librarians, and literacy activists. Secondary data consists of articles, news, and studies relevant to this paper. The research data was collected through observation, interviews, and documentation. The data were analysed using data reduction, presentation, and conclusion-drawing techniques. This study found four strategies to increase the interest in reading in the Majene community: first, implementing the digital reading corner program (POCADI). Second, following the training and development of librarians. Third, socialisation through mobile libraries. Fourth, procurement of sustainable book collections. As a practical implication of this research, it is expected that the Majene Regional Government needs to increase attention to libraries by providing a larger budget for procuring book collections, improving facilities and infrastructure, and training librarians.

Keywords: Reading Interest, Librarian Majene, Strategy.

INTRODUCTION

Reading is a fundamental activity in the development of knowledge and the advancement of human civilization. Through reading activities, people can obtain information, develop insights, and improve critical thinking skills that are indispensable in facing global challenges. However, ironically, reading interest in Indonesia is still relatively low compared to other countries (Heriyudananta, 2021). This is evidenced by data from *Central Connecticut State University* in 2016, which ranked Indonesia 60 out of 61 countries surveyed regarding literacy skills (Dewi et al., 2022). UNESCO data in 2022 showed that the reading interest index in Indonesia only reached 0.001, which means that out of 1000 people, only one person has a high interest in reading. (Nurhasana et al., 2023). This condition is certainly a serious concern for various parties, especially librarians who have a central role in increasing public interest in reading (Nuswantari & Manik, 2023).

Low interest in reading can be caused by various factors, including lack of access to quality and interesting reading materials, ineffective learning methods, the influence of social media and digital technology, and lack of support from family and the environment (Efriza et al., 2023). Low reading interest in Indonesia is an urgent challenge to overcome (Meliyanti & Aryanto, 2022). Low reading interest can be caused by a variety of complex factors, including lack of accessibility to relevant and interesting reading materials, less innovative teaching methods, the dominance of digital technology that distracts from reading, and family and social environments that are less supportive of a reading culture (Heriyudananta, 2021). In addition, economic factors also play an important role, where the relatively expensive price of books is an obstacle for some people (2023). As a result, people prefer watching television and using social media rather than reading, which indicates that reading has not become a primary need in obtaining information (Heriyudananta, 2021). In this context, libraries as information providers and learning resources strategically increase people's interest in reading.

Libraries play an important role in developing human resources and improving the community's quality of life. As an information center, regional libraries are the backbone of education and information dissemination at the regional level, including the Majene Regency Regional Library in West Sulawesi. The existence of libraries has gained a place in the sphere of government with the enactment of Law Number 43 of 2007 concerning libraries. (Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 43, 2007) In a broader context, libraries function not only as a repository for information and communication technology media but also as a center for learning activities, information sources, documentation, and references (AG et al., 2020). Libraries, as the frontline in providing information resources, have a crucial role in fostering a culture of literacy and increasing public interest in reading (Sugiyanta, 2018). According to *the American Library Association*, libraries provide all people with opportunities to learn, explore new ideas, and acquire the knowledge they need to thrive in life, have a career, and participate in society (International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, 2017). Sociologically, the existence of Libraries cannot be separated from the fabric of society. Sociologically, the existence of . Utami & Prasetyo, 2020). To that end, Libraries is inseparable from the fabric of society Libraries must move away from the old paradigm as a repository of books by transforming into a social inclusion-based library that provides extensive benefits to the community (libraries must continue to innovate by adopting new technologies, developing digital collections, and offering services that are relevant to the needs of modern society (Noer'Aida, 2009).

Majene Regency, which has the characteristics of a community with a distinctive culture and local wisdom, requires a special approach that suits the needs and preferences of the local community. Librarians in Majene are faced with the challenge of designing programs that increase interest in reading and are relevant to people's daily lives. In the results of previous research, the problems faced by librarians in increasing the reading interest of the Majene community are limited facilities and infrastructure, a lack of book collections that meet the needs of library users, low public interest in reading, and a lack of socialization and promotion strategies for library services. These problems can hinder efforts to increase public interest in reading in Majene. Librarians, as the spearhead in library management, have a big responsibility to overcome this challenge.

Although various efforts have been made, no comprehensive study has analyzed librarians' strategies for increasing the reading interest of the Majene community. An in-depth understanding of strategies is needed to develop sustainable and impactful literacy programs. Therefore, this study aims to identify and deeply analyze librarians' strategies in increasing the reading interest of Majene people, with the hope of positively contributing to library development and improving the quality of human resources in the Majene area.

RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research is descriptive research (Jonata, 2022). This research approach is qualitative. This research was conducted at the Majene Regency Library and Archives Office. Data sources are obtained from primary and secondary data. Data was collected by observation, interviews, and documents. Data processing techniques, namely, data reduction, data presentation, and conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. RESEARCH RESULTS.

The following are the results of the author's interviews with informants related to the librarian's strategy in increasing the reading interest of the Majene community.

1. Digital Reading Corner. (POCADI).

Based on the results of the author's interview with informant one, who said that:

"The reading corner program is running starting at the end of 2022 with assistance from the National Library. POCADI is a program created by the National Library in collaboration with the Regional Government to facilitate access to information. Majene Regency Library and Archives Office was appointed as one of the recipients of the Digital Reading Corner Assistance in 2022. Only the community response from this program is mostly from junior and senior high school students who

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visit the community; generally, the community is less." (HJ. Suci Jama'ah, personal interview, January 6, 2025)

Similarly, informant two also provided information. Informant 2 said that:

"We also see the need to expand socialization to adults, such as MSME groups or housewife communities, so that they can use POCADI to develop their knowledge in business, children's education, or other relevant skills." (Husnia, personal interview, January 6, 2025).

Furthermore, the results of the author's interview with informant four, who said that:

"As a literacy community, we see this POCADI program as a potential way to bring people closer to digital-based information. However, we also realize that the general public has not been much involved in this program. We are discussing with the library to organize joint activities, such as training on introducing POCADI technology or digital literacy workshops for the community." (Najamuddin, personal interview, January 17, 2025).

Regarding the POCADI program, informant three also gave the same information, saying that:

"We have tried introducing POCADI to various groups, including the public, through social media. However, the response is still not optimal due to their lack of understanding of accessing this digital platform. Many residents still have difficulty using basic technological devices. For this reason, we plan to collaborate with local community groups, literacy communities, youth organizations, or the PKK, to introduce this program." (Murni, personal interview, January 6, 2025)

Based on the author's interviews with four informants, the author concludes that the Digital Reading Corner Program (POCADI) in Majene Regency has great potential to increase access to digital-based information, but still faces challenges in reaching the general public outside of students. The community is less interested in this program because no interesting activities that can make Pocadi known to the community. Therefore, cooperation with various community groups can be a solution to introduce this program.

2. Participate in Librarian Training and Development

Based on the results of the author's interview with informant one, related to increasing librarians' capacity through training. Informant 1 said:

"We encourage librarians to continuously improve their competence by attending various trainings organized by the National Library and other institutions. With this training, librarians are expected to understand new strategies in developing library services that are more interesting and relevant to the community." (HJ. Suci Jama'ah, personal interview, January 6, 2025).

Informant 1 further said that:

"In addition to attending bolding training, we also try to hold regular internal discussions so that librarians can share experiences and solutions related to the obstacles they face in increasing people's interest in reading." (HJ. Suci Jama'ah, personal interview, January 6, 2025).

Furthermore, the interview results from informant 2 said that:

"The activities that have been participated in are training held by the National Library through Zoom in the National Library application, with several materials related to the development of library services and increasing interest in reading through mobile libraries." (Husnia, personal interview, January 6, 2025).

Informant 2 further said that:

"In the training, we learned how to develop more creative library programs, such as interactive reading activities and collaboration with schools to attract more users." (Husnia, personal interview, January 6, 2025).

The same thing was also conveyed by informant three, who said that:

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"We also received training on using digital technology in library services. This helps us introduce digital libraries to the public who may still be unfamiliar with accessing reading materials online." (Murni, personal interview, January 6, 2025).

Furthermore, informant 3 said that:

"After the training, we started implementing new strategies, such as increasing mobile library services and creating community-based literacy programs to reach more readers in remote areas." (Murni, personal interview, January 6, 2025).

As a conclusion from the results of the author's interviews with informants, efforts to increase librarians' capacity through training and development can improve library services in Majene Regency. The training attended, both from the National Library and other institutions, is very important. So it is hoped that the training results can be utilized as well as possible to improve services, especially in increasing the reading interest of the Majene community.

3. Socialization through mobile libraries.

Based on the results of the author's interview with informant one, related to socialization through mobile libraries. Informant 1 said:

"One of our programs here is the mobile library, which is the main strategy to reach the community and visit schools. The initial obstacle was the lack of human resources, but the program could finally run by involving librarians. The response from the community and students was quite positive. In the future, we would like to increase the fleet and establish cooperation with villages, schools, and universities for more structured scheduling." (HJ. Suci Jama'ah, personal interview, January 6, 2025).

Furthermore, the results of the author's interview with informant two, who said that:

"The mobile library is not only about bringing books, but also about interaction. We often organize activities such as reading with students at schools. And apparently, they are more interested in reading novels and other fiction books. We also usually involve the local community to help promote activities related to this mobile library." (Husnia, personal interview, January 6, 2025).

Similar to informant 2, informant three also conveyed the same thing, saying that:

"The mobile library program is expected to be a solution for people who do not have access to libraries. We try to bring various types of reading, including children's books, educational books, and novels, so that people's interest in reading can increase, especially for students as the next generation." (Murni, personal interview, January 6, 2025).

The same thing was also conveyed by informant four, who said that:

"We have collaborated with the mobile library, and the community and students have received the program well. We help socialize the importance of reading books and invite residents to occasionally visit the mobile library if they can, because this will be a good example for children in a neighborhood." (Najamuddin, personal interview, January 17, 2025).

Based on the author's interviews with informants, the author concludes that the mobile library program in Majene District can be a strategy to reach the community, especially in remote areas and schools, by bringing various reading books. This strategy will be better if collaboration with librarians and literacy communities is well-scheduled. This strategy is very good because all communities can access it. So this strategy needs special attention from the government, such as increasing the budget, so that the vehicle facilities used are much better.

4. d. Procurement of Book Collection.

Based on the results of the author's interview with informant one, who explained one of the strategies for increasing public interest in reading. Informant 1 said that:

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"We always try to ensure that the library's book collection reflects the needs of the readers. Therefore, we regularly evaluate and add to the collection with relevant and interesting books." (HJ. Suci Jama'ah, personal interview, January 6, 2025).

The results of the author's interview with informant two, who said that:

"Book procurement is done through various means, such as purchases, donations from literacy communities, and cooperation with publishers and schools. This is a strategic step to keep the collection diverse and updated." (Husnia, personal interview, January 6, 2025).

Furthermore, the results of the author's interview with informant three, who said that:

"We often receive feedback from readers, especially students and teachers, about the types of books they need. This information becomes the basis for determining the books to be added to the library collection, especially in the mobile library." (Murni, personal interview, January 6, 2025).

The same thing was conveyed by informant four, who said that:

"Procuring book collections that align with the times is very important to attract and increase public interest in reading. Relevant and varied books will facilitate information and increase references, increasing reading interest and community visits to the library." (Najamuddin, personal interview, January 17, 2025).

Based on the author's interviews with the four informants, the author concluded that the procurement of book collections is one of the important strategies in increasing public interest in reading in the library. The informants emphasized the importance of regular collection evaluation to ensure that the available books are as expected by the users. This is based on direct input from users such as students and teachers. This strategy is expected to not only enrich information sources but also attract more visits to the library.

B. DISCUSSION

Based on the results of interviews that the author has conducted, we will discuss in more depth the librarian's strategy in increasing the reading interest of the Majene community, which consists of a digital reading program, attending training and librarian development, socialization through mobile libraries, and procuring book collections.

1. Digital Reading Corner. (POCADI)

The digital reading corner program (POCADI) is an initiative of the National Library. This program is listed in the Decree of the Head of the National Library Number 13 of 2022 concerning the Determination of Provincial and Regency Libraries, where the Majene Library and Archives Office is listed in the decree.

In Majene, the digital reading corner program (POCADI) was launched on Wednesday, November 30, 2022, when Hamzah Djamaluddin was the Acting Head of the Majene Library and Archives Office. In the *launching* event, Hamzah Djamaluddin explained that the purpose of the POCADI program is to improve the quality of education in the Majene Region.

Pocadi is a library with print collections, digital collections, bookshelves, digital collection servers, computers, tablets, televisions, and internet access. Pocadi will later become a regional asset as well as an extension service of the Majene Library and Archives Service which is placed in the community, not only preparing reading material in the form of books, but also information through digital that the general public can access, students and students who need digital information (Sam, 2022).

This POCADI program is to introduce digital literacy to students and the Majene community. The location of this POCADI room used to be in the corner of the Prasamya Majene stadium. However, due to the condition of the building, which had begun to deteriorate, such as a leaky roof, POCADI was moved to the Majene Library building. The placement of this POCADI room at the stadium is not without reason, because the stadium is considered closer to the community, and many people have activities in the stadium area, so people will more easily access this POCADI service.

This program has been implemented with the support of the central and local governments. The goal is to facilitate public access to reading materials and digital-based information. However, most visitors to POCADI are elementary, middle, and high school students, while the general public responds less to the program. This suggests that audience segmentation has not been optimized.

Although school students have benefited from POCADI, librarians need to expand the reach of socialization so that this program is more open and can reach other layers of society.

The lack of participation of other communities in the POCADI program may be influenced by several factors, such as a lack of understanding of the program's benefits or the unavailability of content relevant to their needs. For example, MSMEs or housewives may not realize that POCADI can be utilized for business development, children's education, or skills enhancement.

The involvement of literacy communities and related institutions is key in increasing community participation. The planned collaboration between libraries and literacy communities to organize POCADI technology introduction training or digital literacy workshops is a strategic step. Such activities can help the community, especially those less familiar with technology, to understand how to optimally utilize digital facilities.

In the results of research written by (Lutfiah, 2022), it shows To increase the number of library visits, carry out library promotion activities. There are several ways to promote the library, one of which is by conducting user education. Here, user education is carried out using two methods: library orientation and library teaching. These two methods can be utilized according to the wishes and needs of the library.

Library orientation is to introduce facilities, services, and procedures for using the library to new users or those who are not familiar with the library system. For example, an explanation of the rules of conduct or a demonstration of using the digital catalog. Library teaching is a more in-depth activity, such as training or workshops on information literacy skills, such as searching for scientific references, using online databases, or citing sources correctly.

The POCADI program has great potential to increase reading interest and digital literacy in Majene, but needs to be supported by a broader and more targeted strategy. Targeted socialization, collaboration with communities, and provision of content relevant to the needs of the adult community are the keys to success. With these steps, POCADI will not only be a tool for students, but it can also become a learning center for all levels of Majene society.

2. Participate in Librarian Training and Development

Capacity building of librarians through training is one of the strategies in optimizing library services and increasing public interest in reading. Librarians' participation in training organized by the National Library (Perpusnas) and other institutions has equipped librarians with new skills to design creative programs, such as interactive reading activities and collaboration with schools. The training not only focuses on developing conventional services but also covers using digital technology, such as digital library platforms and online-based service systems.

The outcome of the training attended by librarians was implementing the mobile library program. Librarians learned to organize interactive reading activities like storytelling sessions or book discussions to attract children and teenagers. In addition, collaboration with schools is a strategy to reach out to library users from an early age.

Digital technology has become a major focus in librarian capacity building. Training on digital library services, such as e-book access and library apps, has enabled librarians to introduce new ways of accessing information to the public. However, challenges remain, especially in reaching out to communities that are less familiar with technology. To address this, librarians must design community-based digital literacy programs, such as training on digital platforms for housewives or community groups.

In addition to external training, regular internal discussions are important for sharing knowledge and solutions among librarians. This forum allows librarians to reflect on obstacles in the field, such as low community participation. For example, a mobile library program could be developed to target elementary and high school students.

Training and capacity building of librarians are essential in creating library services that meet the community's needs. Strategies such as technical skills enhancement, collaboration with educational institutions, and literacy communities are key to the success of this strategy. By continuously strengthening human resources' capacity, libraries will become literacy centers that can answer the challenges of the digital era.

As the word of Allah.SWT. in QS. At-Taubah (9: 122) which reads:

﴿ وَمَا كَانَ الْمُؤْمِنُونَ لِيَنْفِرُوا كَافَّةً ۚ فَلَوْلَا نَفَرَ مِنْ كُلِّ فِرْقَةٍ مِّنْهُمْ طَائِفَةٌ لِّيَتَفَقَّهُوا فِي الدِّينِ وَلِيُنذِرُوا قَوْمَهُمْ إِذَا رَجَعُوا إِلَيْهِمْ لَعَلَّهُمْ يَحْذَرُونَ ۝١٢٢﴾

Translation:

"It is not fitting that the believers should all go (to war). Why should not some of each group among them go (to stay with the Messenger of Allah) to deepen their knowledge of religion and to warn their people when they return, so that they may protect themselves?" (Ministry of Religious Affairs, 2015).

According to M. Quraish Shihab in (Rohman, 2016), giving His explanation of QS. In the Taubah verse 122, this verse shows the need to understand knowledge well and provide information or share the knowledge obtained. This verse also instructs humans to divide tasks; some follow the armed war, and others remain with the Prophet. Studying religious knowledge. Thus, when the diaspora returned, the two parts shared and complemented each other.

In the context of librarian training in Majene, this can be applied by dividing tasks based on expertise. Some librarians focus on mastering technology (for example, managing POCADI or digital systems), while others develop community literacy programs or direct services. Once trained, they must share this knowledge with their fellow librarians. With this strategy, the skills of the team or librarians can improve evenly, so that the goal of increasing interest in reading in Majene can be achieved.

3. Socialization through mobile libraries.

After attending training and developing various service innovations, librarians focused on a more direct approach to the community: running a mobile library program. If the library had only operated in buildings previously, then the mobile library would reach out to communities with limited access to literacy facilities, especially schools.

Mobile libraries serve communities or educational institutions far from regional city libraries or schools that do not yet have libraries. Mobile libraries have a significant role in instilling a reading culture among the community, especially students.

In the results of research written by Aini Hidayah and Erna Zumrotun, (2024), revealed that the regional mobile library has a very significant role in increasing students' interest in reading This is indicated by the presentation of student reading interest questionnaires included in a very strong category, with a presentation of 55.55%.

Furthermore, the results of research from (SARI, 2023), explain That mobile library managers play a very important role in increasing children's interest in reading, it can be seen by implementing reading interest strategies, teaching and learning and reading stalls so that children more easily understand the learning provided through this activity so that children's interest in reading can be said to increase.

The mobile library strategy expands the scope of library services and introduces a culture of reading to people not accustomed to accessing libraries directly. With the existence of mobile libraries, it is hoped that public interest in reading can increase, especially for the next generation.

Having a diverse collection of books is another key in this strategy. By bringing a variety of books, such as children's stories, education, and novels, the mobile library will succeed in attracting public interest, especially students, as the next generation. Research published by IFLA in *the Global*

Vision Report reveals that collection diversity is a determining factor in the success of literacy programs, because it can answer different information needs (International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, 2017). In Majene, this effort is accompanied by socialization about the importance of reading, especially to parents, so they become examples for children in their environment.

Collaboration with literacy communities and educational institutions is so key to the sustainability and success of the program. For example, collaboration with schools and universities for structured scheduling of visits and involving community leaders in socialization.

4. Book Collection Procurement.

Procuring a relevant and diverse book collection is an important strategy to increase people's interest in reading in Majene Regency. Library librarians in Majene routinely conduct collection evaluations to ensure that library materials, such as current educational, fiction, and reference books, match readers' needs.

The book procurement strategy does not rely solely on purchasing, but also involves donations from the literacy community and cooperation with publishers and schools. This multidimensional approach allows libraries to acquire books cost-effectively while maintaining a diverse collection. For example, cooperation with schools enables the procurement of textbooks that align with the curriculum. At the same time, donations from the literacy community enrich the collection of fiction and light reading books.

As said by (Anawati, 2017) in his research, the completeness of the library collection is an attraction for a library; this causes users to want to come and then want to use the library. Besides that, the collection's sophistication is adjusted to the progress of science so that users can freely search for the information they need.

According to (Sutarno, 2006), the library must complete the collection needed or desired by its customers. The availability of the collection is closely related to its utilization. If the available collection is complete and ready to be used by users, of course, the collection will be utilized by library users. What is needed by users is the availability of books according to their needs. In Majene, this effort is also implemented in the mobile library service, where the book collection is adjusted to the characteristics of the community at each visit location.

(Imam et al., 2024), also revealed that public library services are key to achieving user satisfaction, especially in providing references and the book lending process. The main basis for ensuring user satisfaction is the availability of references that suit users' needs (such as educational books, fiction, history, and culture). Majene's effective lending process, supported by a collection that is constantly updated through direct input from users (students, teachers) and collaboration with the community, strengthens the accessibility of reading. Thus, the quality of lending services depends on administrative procedures and the library's ability to provide collections that meet users' needs.

A collection relevant to the times is a determining factor in the success of this strategy. Up-to-date books on technology, social issues, or digital literacy attract young people who want to broaden their horizons. In addition, various reading genres, such as novels, educational comics, or inspirational books, can reach different age groups.

As in the word of Allah. SWT in QS. Al-Alaq (96: 1-5) which reads:

اقْرَأْ بِاسْمِ رَبِّكَ الَّذِي خَلَقَ الْإِنْسَانَ مِنْ عَلَقٍ اقْرَأْ وَرَبُّكَ الْأَكْرَمُ الَّذِي عَلَّمَ بِالْقَلَمِ عَلَّمَ الْإِنْسَانَ مَا لَمْ يَعْلَمْ

Translation:

- "1. Recite in the name of your Lord who created!
2. He created man from a clot of blood.

3. *Read! Your Lord is the Most Glorious,*
4. *Who teaches (man) with a pen?*
5. *He taught man what he did not know."* (Ministry of Religious Affairs, 2015)

According to (Shihab, 2021), in His book Tafsir Al Misbah explains that the word iqra' or the command to read in a series of verses above, repeats twice, namely in verses 1 and 3. The first command is intended to learn about something that is not yet known, while the second is to teach knowledge to others. This indicates that in learning and learning, maximum effort is required by functioning all components in the form of potential tools that exist in humans. After the knowledge is obtained through learning, the next mandate is to teach the knowledge, while still utilizing all the potential.

The book procurement strategy at Majene Library is relevant to M. Quraish Shihab's explanation in Tafsir Al-Misbah regarding the command to read (iqra'). In the interpretation, he explains that the command to read is not only a process of acquiring knowledge, but also involves the responsibility to spread knowledge to others. This is in line with the library's main function as a literacy center that provides reading resources and ensures that the community can maximally utilize the available knowledge.

In book procurement, the iqra principle can be applied by ensuring that the books provided in the Majene Library meet the needs and development of science. The books selected should cover various disciplines relevant to the local community's needs, both in the educational, social, cultural, and economic fields. In addition, the library should also pay attention to the availability of books that support the improvement of skills and insights of the community, so that they can gain new knowledge and apply it in their daily lives.

Besides providing books, libraries are also responsible for spreading knowledge effectively. This can be done through literacy programs, book discussions, reading training, and providing digital access for those who cannot come directly to the library. So that the library is not only a place to store books, but also plays an active role in the learning process of the community, as the Qur'an commandment *requires* humans to not only learn, but also teach knowledge to others.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results, it can be concluded that the librarian's strategy in increasing the reading interest of Majene people is to create a digital reading program, train and develop librarians, promote socialization through mobile libraries, and procure sustainable book collections. As an implication of this research, the Majene Regional Government needs to increase attention to libraries by providing a larger budget for procuring book collections, improving facilities and infrastructure, and training librarians.

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